

INTERESTING AND EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

Haitova Shahzoda Turg'un qizi

Student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Scientific supervisor: **Zubaydova Nilufar Nematullayevna**

Teacher of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Abstract: This article discusses various methods of fast, effective and interesting teaching of English, which are popular in many countries around the world today. Below is how to explain to children the important role of English today and how to attract the attention of elementary and high school students in English language learning with various active and interesting methods.

Key words: english language teaching methodology, activity, scientists' opinion, memory, attention, methods, writing, communication, purpose, modern technologies, games

INTRODUCTION

In the rapidly changing times, learning and teaching English offers a wide range of opportunity. For this reason, the Cabinet of Ministers made decisions to take the popularization of foreign language teaching to a new level and develop the field in our country. For example, according to the decision of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the State Budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022" of the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Public Education and the Agency for Popularization of Foreign Language Learning under the Cabinet of Ministers funds were allocated. It certainly created new opportunities to strengthen the teaching of English. Today, the people of the world want to learn English faster in easy and interesting ways. Taking into account that interest and attention play an important role in language learning, teachers are also trying to find new and convenient methods and methods of teaching English. There are many ways and methods of teaching English.

Method of use of interesting resources

It is a way of using different materials to make English interesting, effective, fast, convenient and viable, which makes learning the language more interactive and practical. This method is especially suitable for people of all ages. Below is detailed information on how and what to use this method: *Movies and tv series*: it is recommended to watch with subtitles at the beginning and without subtitles later.

Older people and people with disabilities can easily learn and even be motivated by watching movies. Movies and series are good for learning a language, because through them you can hear live communication, pronunciation and expressions. *Musics*: Music can be used to develop hearing in children. Age-appropriate music is chosen for the children and they are taught to pronounce the music using various movements. As a result, hearing and pronunciation are well developed in children 1st graders in particular learn the language through a variety of fun, role-playing games, stories, songs and activities.

Dealing with errors in oral english

Nowadays, teachers struggle to find an answer to the question of whether or not to point out students' mistakes. In such a situation, teachers should create a traditional and free classroom environment, that is, students are friendly to each other. should create conditions for him to correct his mistakes. For example, it should provide different scenarios and teamwork tasks. Through these tasks, they can be close to each other and even evaluate many people at the same time.

Theory of constructivism

According to him, education is a process in which knowledge is created with the help of the student's thinking activity, and no one teaches anything to anyone, the student must learn. That is, people do not receive ready-made ideas from anyone, but create them themselves. The child should learn using experiments, prepare different models, schemes, find answers to controversial questions, that is, learn with the method of "doing it in practice". Through this method, children learn the language in the ways they are interested in. can learn, act independently and help children remember quickly, easily and better. Because in today's globalized era, children like to move freely.

The cinquevine method

This is a French word that means "five lines," meaning a five-line rhymeless poem. the teacher writes poems even if the rhymes do not match within a topic and memorizes them as poems or music to the students. through this method, even the children will memorize it with interest as a regular poem and will not forget it. It can also be used as a lyrical digression or daily motto when set to music.

CONCLUSION

Of course, it is more difficult for a person to learn other languages, because he has to learn unfamiliar words, unfamiliar pronunciation and a different worldview. But today's modern technologies and various guides of our scientists make it easier for people to learn. In conclusion the most important thing in learning a language is

to have a sincere desire, to set a clear goal, and to be able to take advantage of technology and opportunities. Pronunciation and listening are important in English. In addition, it is important to use methods and methods appropriate to the age and interest of people in teaching English, to be able to form friendly communication with them. Children should be especially attracted by interactive games.

THE LIST OF LITERATURE

1. D Nu'monova, U Qo'Ziyev Badiiy matni lingvostatistik tomondan tahlil qilish *Oriental Art and Culture*, 119-121, 2020
2. M Orzikulova, G Rustamova "Methods Of Improving Speaking Skills For Kids" *Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit*, 151-154, 2024
3. N Dedamirzayeva, U Kuziyev Teaching English to young learners through games *Oriental Art and Culture*, 86-88, 2020
4. N N Zubaydova How to teach vocabulary *Nofilolog oliy o'quv yurtlarida chet tilini o'qitishda uchraydigan muammolar ...*, 2019
5. R S Sharipovna. Peculiarities Of Teaching English In Secondary Schools In Uzbekistan *International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology*, 1-5,
6. K Khashimova, U Kuziev Participation Of Languages Of Other Systems In The Formation Of The Uzbek Literary Language *Збірник наукових праць ЛОГОС*, 22-25, 2020
7. R. A Utkurovich, R. G Utkurovna. "Teaching English Language To Primary Level Pupils At School" *Ijodkor O'qituvchi* 3 (36), 103-105, 2024.
8. U Qo'ziyev Tilda Soflik Masalasi Ta'limda Turkiy Xalqlar Milliy Mentalitetini Mustahkamlashning Dolzarb ..., 2022.
9. G. U Rustamova *Lingvistik Pragmatikaning Birliklari. Филологические науки* 11, 0.
10. Ikromjonovna, J. S. (2024). Usmon Azimning "Baxshiyona" Larida Tabiat Tasvirining Ifoda Etilish Usullari. *Analysis of International Sciences*, 2(6), 11-16.
11. Ikromjonovna, J. S. (2024). Usmon Azim Peyzajining O 'Ziga Hos Xususiyatlari. *Analysis of International Sciences*, 2(6), 17-24.
12. Ikromjonovna, J. S., & Sevara, A. (2024). O 'Qish Savodxonligi Darslarida O 'Quvchilar Bilimini Baholash Usullari. *Kokand University Research Base*, 261-265.
13. Ikromjonovna, J. S., & Moxira, T. (2024). Boshlang 'Ich Hamda Maktabgacha Ta'lim Tashkilotlari Ta'lim-Tarbiya Jarayonida Multimedia Texnologiyasidan Foydalanish. *Kokand University Research Base*, 256-260.

14. Ikromjonovna, J. S., & Ikromjon o'g'li, P. H. (2024). Ona Tili Va O 'Qish Darslarida Pisa Xalqaro Dasturidan Foydalanish. Kokand University Research Base, 242-249.
15. Ikromjonovna, J. S., & Muazzamxon, X. (2024). 4-Sinf O 'Qish Savodxonligi Darslarida Pirls Xalqaro Baholash Dasturlaridan Foydalanish. Kokand University Research Base, 250-255.
16. Jumanova, S. (2023). Usmon Azim She'riyatida Metaforalarning O 'Ziga Xos Xususiyatlari. Namangan davlat universiteti Ilmiy axborotnomasi, (11), 292-297.
17. Бойназаров, И. (2012). Дастурлаш асослари бўйича мультимедиали ўргатувчи тизимни ўқув жараёнига жорий этиш. Экономика и инновационные технологии, (3), 86-90.
18. Валиева, Н. А. (2023). 1917 Ўил Февраль-Октябрь Оралигида Туркистон. Golden Brain, 1(30), 208-214.
19. Abdumajitovna, V. N. (2023). Russian Colonial Policy In Turkestan- Establishment Of A Centralized Administrative System. International Journal Of Social Science & Interdisciplinary Research ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 8.036, 12(01), 54-57.
20. Sunnatillayevna, A. Y. (2024). The Innovative Method Of Learn Foreign Languages In Different Countries. Journal of Computational Analysis and Applications (JoCAAA), 33(05), 744-747.
21. Abulkasimova, Y. (2024). Foreign Language Communicative Competence For Students Of Non-Philological Educational Profiles. Builders Of The Future, 4(04), 109-113.
22. Abulkasimova, Y. (2023). The Essence Of The Development Of Communicative Competence In Teaching English. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 71-75.
23. Abulkasimova, Y. (2023). Didactic Requirements For Effective Teaching Of English In Higher Education Residences. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(21), 164-166.
24. Abulkasimova, Y. (2023). Teacher's Role And The Principles Of Teaching Speaking Skill. Talqin va tadqiqotlar, 1(11).
25. Jumayeva, M. B. (2023). Chet Tillarini O'rganishda Ommaviy Axborot Vositalarining O'rni va Ahamiyati. Boshqaruv va Etika Qoidalari Onlayn Ilmiy Jurnal, 3(5), 240-242.

26. Jumayeva, M. B. (2023). Classifications of Cardinal Numbers and Ordinal Numbers in English And Uzbek. *Ijtimoiy Fanlarda Innovasiya Onlayn Ilmiy Jurnal*, 3(2), 132-134.
27. Ochilova, G., & Ashurova, N. (2022). Semantic features of English narrative text. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 12(5), 279-283.
28. Ashurova, N., Suleymanova, N., Amanov, A., & Aslonov, F. (2023). Conceptual Framework for the Design of Electronic Textbook for EFL Students. *Journal of Higher Education Theory & Practice*, 23(16).
29. Ashurova, N. (2019). The use of advertising texts in teaching a foreign language. In *Science and Practice: A New Level of Integration in the Modern World* (pp. 190-192).
30. Jumayev, F. B., & Jumayev, B. N. (2023). Ways to Improve Listening Skills Among Children. *Ijtimoiy Fanlarda Innovasiya Onlayn Ilmiy Jurnal*, 3(2), 129-131.